

SMARANDACHE SOCIAL SEMI-PARADOX:

In a democracy should the non-democratic ideas be allowed?

a) If no, i.e. other ideas are not allowed - even those non-democratic -, then one not has a democracy, because the freedom of speech is restricted.

b) If yes, i.e. the non-democratic ideas are allowed, then one might end up to a non-democracy (because the non-democratic ideas could overthrow the democracy as, for example, it happened in Nazi Germany, in totalitarian countries, etc.).

Reference:

Smarandache, Florentin, "Neutrosophy. / Neutrosophic Probability, Set, and Logic", American Research Press, Rehoboth, 1989.